

LINGUOPRAGMATIC ASPECTS OF THE SPEECH ACT IN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Annotation: The article discusses about the concept of a speech act, its study, classification by scientists and types, as well as the stages of a speech act. The field of intercultural pragmatics is briefly described, paying attention to the speech act and intercultural communication, focusing on the features of the speech act that affect intercultural communication. Also, examples of speech acts that are used differently in different cultures in a specific situation are given and analyzed.

Key words: pragmalinguistics, speech act, linguaculture, illocution, perlocution, location, pragmatic analysis.

Many scientists have shown interest in the problem of the relationship between language and culture, language and thinking, and research is still being conducted. Prominent scientists of the 19th century I. Herder, A.V. Schlegel, W. von Humboldt, A. Schleicher, A. Potebnya and others tried to understand the principles of language development, to determine the relationship between language and thinking, to understand the nature of language and to create a general theory of language. In recent years, the anthropocentric paradigm has gained the main importance in the science of linguistics. Placing a person in the center of language units and showing his diversity created a new direction in linguistics and laid the foundation for a number of new sciences. In our following small study, the concept of speech act, which is considered the main object of pragmalinguistics, its study and the reflection of cultural diversity in it, will be analyzed.

Cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, and pragmalinguistics are fields that deal with the interaction between language and culture, language and thought. A. Vejbitskaya, V. Vorobyev, Y. Karaulova, V. Maslova, V. Telia and others have widely revealed the theoretical foundations of linguistic culture. Linguistics is considered as a philological science that studies the relationship and interaction of culture and language, cultural values in language, moral, aesthetic and cognitive values encoded in language, as well as views and beliefs of

representatives of one culture, individual and social also studies their relationships.

In turn, the new paradigm called anthropocentrism, which calls for the study of the individual as a holistic phenomenon, made it possible to perceive a person in relation to his language, as a person of language, and the human factor came to the fore in the center of new fields, therefore, in modern linguistics, scientists in the field of pragmalinguistics, did great things. The phenomenon of interest to linguists became the theory of speech acts, and it became the general object of pragmalinguistics. The theory of speech acts is one of the branches of analytical philosophy. In the late 1940s, Austin brought the theory of speech act into science and emphasized that the important point for pragmalinguistics is not only the ability to construct sentences, but also the ability to use speech acts correctly to achieve the desired communicative functional result.

[J. Austin 1986:131] As J. Austin said: "...to say something is to do it."

[J. Austin 1986:131] J. Austin was the first to propose the name speech act.

For example, the word "Yes" or "I agree" is said during the marriage ceremony. The term proposed by J. Austin shows that the production of a sentence is the realization of an action, because in such a situation the word does not remain as such, but becomes an action, which means, i.e. "Yes" or "I agree" now means that he will get married. For the first time, the scientist divides the purposeful speech of people into groups. As we know, J. Austin divides the speech act into 5 categories. These are:

1. Verdicts (speech acts concerning judges)
2. Exercises (speech acts expressing desire)
3. Commissives (speech acts related to a promise)
4. Behabitives (speech acts related to etiquette, manners)
5. Expository (speech acts that express proof, reason and message)

These groups are applied in verbal and non-verbal situations in real life, in relation to the moment of speech and exhortation to a certain action based on a certain reason.

After the initial basic views were carried out by J. Austin, J.R. Serlem and N.M. Wachteler studies this direction and according to them, a speech act is "speech communication that is spoken for a specific purpose and addressed to the interlocutor in order to achieve a specific desired result." [Serlem, 1991 7:200].

For communicative speech, special attention is paid not only to the participants of the speech, but also to the specific situation, culture, age, and social status of the interlocutors.

To date, the concept of "speech act" is defined as follows:

a) In the linguistic encyclopedic dictionary, a speech act is "a purposeful speech act performed in accordance with the principles and rules of speech behavior accepted in a particular society; units of normative social speech behavior are an object to be studied within the framework of a pragmatic situation. [Huang, Yan, 2014:56].

b) Uzbek scientist M. Khakimov defines it as follows: "It is the verbal communication of speakers in the process of interaction-intervention related to the speech situation". [M. Khakimov 2020:35].

The speech act is analyzed in two ways:

1. Linguistic
2. Pragmatic

According to J. Austin, if we study how the speech act is analyzed through the pattern of words and sentences, and from the pragmatic side, in what situation, what words to use, to whom and where, we analyze the occurrence of the speech act in the addresser and the addressee. If we analyze it pragmatically, it can be expressed not only with words, but also through non-verbal means (face turning, shrugging, intonation, etc.). Both processes will be in 3 stages, according to J. Austin. These are locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary. A locative act is a statement of something that can be given some meaning. This act consists of three subordinate acts:

1. **Phonetic** (in oral speech - sound articulation according to phonetic rules, in writing - graphic record of the statement according to spelling rules);
2. **Phatic** (formation of the sound range in accordance with the rules of word formation and connection);
3. **Rhetoric** (using words and sentences in accordance with the semantic rules of the language).

The concept of "illocative act" is defined in pragmalinguistics as an action performed by a person in the speech process and as a means of speech activity. According to O.G. Pochepsov:

- 1) the executor of the illocutionary act is the speaker or writer;
- 2) the illocutionary act differs from speech creation activity;
- 3) illocutionary act occurs in the process of speech creation;
- 4) the illocutionary act is performed as a means of speech activity.

It was mentioned above that any communicative act is performed with a final goal in mind.

This speech activity is the main cause that serves the completion of the speech act. To achieve this goal, the speech of the speaker needs to influence the listener. The influencing stage of speech activity is called the perlocutionary act. We see the result of the utterance of the sentence "I made hot tea" when the listener accepts this speech act for the purpose we want (for example, when the listener hears that the tea is hot and agrees to drink it). So, perlocution is an act of influencing the mind, feelings and behavior of the listener. The main position on which the theory of speech acts is based is that the minimum unit of human communication is not a sentence or a word, but a question, command, promise, statement, explanation, thanks, apology, greeting, congratulations, request and is to perform a certain type of action like others. As the object of study in the theory of speech acts, which consists of pronouncing sentences by the speaker in the conditions of direct communication with the listener, is considered. Therefore, the theory of speech acts is characterized by the maximum narrowing of the object of study, which distinguishes it from other theories. This situation, on the one hand, limited the possibilities of the theory of speech acts, and on the other hand, it allowed us to focus on the detailed description of the internal structure of the speech act.

These two concepts - the elements of linguistic culture, which we mentioned above, are reflected in the speech act by itself. Because the specific situation of the speakers is taken into account in the speech act, then their language culture also has an impact on communication. Observing that the object of the speech act of pragmatics does not occur only between representatives of one culture, scientists pay attention to the prevention of cultural shock between two different cultures by connecting the speech act with culturology. The connection between language and culture was first noted in the scheme of the American linguist R. Lado at the beginning of the 20th century. At present, the idea of the anthropocentricity of language is generally recognized, in this regard, the person in the language and the language in the person are analyzed. As Baudouin de Courtenay pointed out, "language exists only in individual brains, only in souls, only in the psyche of individuals who make up a certain linguistic community" [Blum-Kulka, Shoshana, Juliane House, and Gabriele Casper 1989:39].

Although speech act and culture are different semiotic systems, they have a lot in common. V.N. According to Telia:

- 1) culture, like language, is a form of consciousness that reflects a person's worldview;
- 2) culture is reflected together with language in the process of speech act expression;
- 3) the subject of culture and language is always a person or society.
- 4) normativity is a common feature of culture and language;

6) the antinomy of dynamics-statics is characteristic of culture and speech process [Telia 2005:217].

Through the above points, he once again emphasizes that the culture to which the speaker belongs, linguistic and non-linguistic units, are definitely involved in speech acts, in speech activity in general.

Intercultural communication, in turn, has a distinct interdisciplinary nature and can be studied within the framework of pragmalinguistics. To be more precise, pragmalinguistics deals directly with the results of intercultural interaction. The subject of pragmalinguistics is the study of the exchange of ideas between certain individuals in a specific situation using verbal and non-verbal means of communication, how a person uses these means to convey his intentions to the interlocutor or the student in certain life conditions. Pragmalinguistics studies aspects of language and culture to some extent, but unlike intercultural communication, real-time communication is studied. Pragmalinguistics studies the characteristics of the communicative process in people.

In the process of speech act, people with different customs and traditions show different types of speech act directly and indirectly. Because the speech act is a minimal means of linguistic communication and reflects the intercultural characteristics and means of expression of a person belonging to a certain culture. People with different cultures face certain difficulties in the process of everyday speech act. For example, representatives of different linguistic and cultural groups, even when communicating in the same language, act according to "their" patterns of behavior, relying on their knowledge of culture and etiquette, and therefore the rules of etiquette pragmatically significant structures are different and in some cases can be implemented in various inappropriate acts according to the situation of communicative communication. A speech act, whether verbal or non-verbal, varies culturally. For example, there is a lot of diversity in non-verbal communication acts. For example, if the carriers of Kazakh culture hug and shake hands, it means showing respect, kindness, and sympathy to each other, while for the Chinese, it means disrespect. Such situations are manifested in many nations in different forms.

This, of course, affects the speech act process. Even in Turkic peoples, when there is a mourning ceremony, crying out loud is considered a symbol of respect and attention for the family, while in Chinese it is absolutely impossible to cry, it is customary to look at the dead person with a smile and express the best wishes for the deceased. In Western countries, it is customary to say warm thoughts for the deceased, to express the best feelings and good deeds of

the deceased during the funeral ceremony. Uzbeks use negative speech acts in this ceremony. For example, in the sense of apologizing, a speech act is performed: "Wow, dad, I couldn't take good care of you, I couldn't serve you". "Forgive your ill-mannered son" can be cited. The Chinese use the speech act of congratulation more often in this process. For example, "I congratulate you on your departure to a new destination", "You are about to start your second life", and in the sense of a wish "I congratulate you on your departure to the real and eternal world", "I wish you to live happily in this world".

In Western times, the speech act towards the deceased is expressed by expressing gratitude. For example, "Dad, thank you for raising me well!" They create a speech act with the good qualities of the deceased, such as "James, thank you for never leaving us and supporting us." Such examples can be given a lot in all types of speech acts. Because each nation has its own cultural and communicative aspects. Cultural and communicative means considered normal for some people and nations are considered abnormal for another. Such aspects are mainly observed in the differences between two different cultures in ceremonies, various traditions, greetings, etiquette, and respect.

There are certain factors related to the choice of language tools and communicative tactics in any speech act. Usually, these factors are universal for all cultures, and certain parameters, principles, and postulates have been developed in this regard. These are the age parameter, the gender of the communicators, the communicators belonging to the same or different ethnic groups, social status, the factor of familiarity or unfamiliarity, the factor of the situation of communication. These factors are very important for the correct understanding of the speech act. Because if we take this into account in the speech process, any communication process will be successful. If a speech act occurs between the owners of the same culture, its pragmatic aspects prevail and it is smoothly followed. Because in this process the linguistic and cultural codes common to the addresser and the addressee merge. If the speech act takes place between two different cultures, cultural stereotypes come to the fore. To date, one of the directions of speech act theory and pragmalinguistics has as its main goal, the study of postulates of communication, that is, the principles or rules of everyday human communication. In this situation, it is not enough to study and apply the theory of the speech act.

Studying the speech act psycholinguistically, sociolinguistically and, of course, linguoculturologically - reveals that the meaningful structures of the speech act, i.e. request, command, gratitude, threat, respect, etc., are expressed differently in different cultures, it allows to identify the similar and different aspects in them. This can greatly contribute to preventing cultural

shock in the era of globalization and strengthening intercultural mutual respect. For this purpose, it is relevant to research how speech acts are performed in certain languages, in particular, languages of different or the same family, which linguistic tools are dominant in them, and the role of speech acts in successful intercultural communication.

To conclude, as Cedar states, "language is dance, and culture is music. When dance and music are in harmony, they bring joy to the dancers". In our next researches, a wide research of similar and different aspects of speech acts, specific aspects of verbal and non-verbal expression will continue in our next research.

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